

The Impact of Digital Economy on Bank Customers' Satisfaction in South-South, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the impact of digital economy on bank customers satisfaction in South- South States, in Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design. The sample size of 384 was determined using a formula for an infinite population proposed by Godden (2004). Primary data were collected through the use of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed in a 5-point Likert scale format and validated by ensuring content, concurrent, convergent, and discriminant validity. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined using Cronbach's Alpha. Three hundred and seventy-two (372), representing 97%, were retrieved and adjudged usable for the study. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the research hypothesis. The study data analysis revealed that digital economy has a significant impact on bank customer satisfaction. Specifically, the result shows that the adoption of digital in banking economy such as mobile banking app (MOB) with a coefficient value of ($\beta = .864$; $t = 11.798$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in the mobile banking app affects an 86.4% positive change in customer satisfaction. The result shows that Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) with a coefficient value of ($\beta = .118$; $t = 2.365$; $p = 0.019 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) affects about a 12% positive change in customer satisfaction. Likewise, the result shows that a Point of Sale (POS) with a coefficient value of ($\beta = -0.498$; $t = -5.608$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in Point of Sale affects a 49.8%, about 50% decline in customer satisfaction. Lastly, the result shows that the Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) with a coefficient value of ($\beta = 0.559$; $t = 14.334$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in Automatic Teller Machine effects 55.9%, approximately 56% positive change in bank customer satisfaction. Based on these findings, the study recommends that digital economy via digital banking channels should be embracing and encourage by all Nigerian and, that governments at all levels should formulate and implement the policies that will improve the use of digital economy. Also, stakeholders in financial sector should improving digital economy infrastructures that will aid the performance of the digital banking channels as well as contributes to customer satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Digital Economy, Banking Customers Satisfaction, Mobile Banking App, Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD and Point of Sale (POS))

1. INTRODUCTION

Bank customer satisfaction is considered to be a crucial factor in determining success in the bank industries in today's highly competitive business environment. This is because satisfied bank customers are more likely to remain loyal and refer others which contribute to stability, profitability and growth of the bank. Nevertheless, achieving bank customer satisfaction is not an easy task, due to the human needs complexity. In today digital world customers are becoming tough to please, smarter, more conscious of the cost of services, and are frequently approached by many more bank and financial related companies with the same or improved banking services .

In the same vain, bank customer expectations are increasing regarding how quickly service providers respond, the breadth and depth of interaction and communication, customization of product and service offerings, as well as the rapid changes in customer demands, desires, and expectations (Abdulrauf, Tinuoye, Quadr & Akosile, 2022). As a result, what satisfied and impressed them a short time ago may no longer do so.

The increasingly fierce competition in the banking industry has made bank customer satisfaction the focal point of the stakeholder's in banks' industry regarding the product and service decisions. According to Nwobum, Ngaikedi, and Anyanwu (2022)

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organizations gain a competitive edge by effectively identifying and meeting customer needs through superior products and services. Subsequently, adoption of digital economy in the bank industries is one of the key areas that financial institutions worldwide are leverage on to satisfy.

The term digital economy is coined by Don Tapscott in his 1995 book. It define it as promise and perils in the networked age. However in relation to banking, digital economy; refers to a technology or networking channel through which financial institutions conduct their activities, moving away from traditional brick-and-mortar banking, which involves face-to-face interactions at the counter. It utilizes digital technologies and internet-enabled platforms to deliver banking services without the need for physical bank branches. Bank customers no longer need to wait in line for hours to be served to by tellers or staff. This is as a result of advancement in technology and network connectivity, bank customers can now be served promptly. Various aspects of digital economy banking in Nigeria include mobile banking apps (MOB), Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD), Point of Sale (POS) systems, Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs), and more.

These aforementioned platforms have played a vital role in improving service delivery, making processes more efficient and customer-friendly. However, each of them has its shortcoming which also result to customer dissatisfaction. Ranges from none availability of cash in the ATM, card trapped in the ATM, excessive extra charges for cash withdrawal and deposit, transaction declines, network issues, among others. The implication therein is that an unsatisfied customer will most likely not recommend the provider to other customers and this can cause the bank to lose customers to other competitors. It is on this context that this study examines the impact of digital economy on bank customer satisfaction in selected States of South-south in, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Despite, huge amount associated in embracing digital economy in bank industry to satisfy bank customers. Unanticipated shortcoming of digital economy have equally resulted to bank customers dissatisfaction. As a result customers switch from one bank digital platform to another, consequently, some digital channel become unprofitable to the bank causing decline in their customer base, market share, and profit margin. However, several empirical studied in the past on the impact of digital economy on bank customers satisfaction produced mixed outcomes and inconclusiveness. While some studies like Shariff, Abubakar, and Haruna (2025); Bindiya, & Kishor, (2025); Godwin (2024); Shariff, Abubakar & Usman (2024) concluded that adoption of digital economy in banking industries have positive impact on bank customers satisfaction others opinion like Ukwubile and Onwe (2024); Nwarisi, Igwe & Ozuru (2022); Asuquo & Ezekwe, (2020); Chimaobi, Akujor and Mbah (2020) stated otherwise. Hence, identify the impact of digital economy on bank customers satisfaction is imperative in order to improve bank performance and enhancing bank customer satisfaction.

Objective of the study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the impact of digital economy on bank customers' satisfaction in South-south States, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. Examine the impact of the mobile online banking app on customer satisfaction
- ii. Investigate the impact of Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) on customer satisfaction
- iii. Determine the impact of Point of Sale (POS) on customer satisfaction
- iv. Ascertain the impact of the Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) on customer satisfaction

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Digital Economy

The digital economy is the global economic activity based on digital technologies, encompassing online connections, transactions, and services like e-commerce, digital banking, streaming, and AI, transforming traditional sectors by leveraging the internet, mobile tech, data, and connectivity to create new value, streamline processes, and reach customers globally. It's characterized by data-driven personalization, automation, and hyperconnectivity, fundamentally altering how businesses operate and people consume goods and services, shifting from physical to digital interactions.

(<https://www.techtarget.com/searchcio/definition/digital-economy>; Adegioriola, Jimoh & Oladele, 2021; Nwoke (2024) describes digital banking as a customer-centric approach to banking that leverages technology to simplify transactions, improve service delivery, and provide real-time access to financial services.

2.1.2 Concept of Customer Satisfaction

According to Oliver (2022) customer satisfaction is a customer's overall assessment of their experience with a service or product, based on what they expected versus what they actually received. For digital banking, this means looking at how satisfied people are with factors like how fast their transactions are, how easy the platform is to use, how secure they feel, and how accessible

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customer support is. Shariff, Abubakar, and Haruna (2025) describe customer satisfaction in banking as a reflection of how well the bank meets the customer's expectations in terms of the quality, convenience, and responsiveness of its services. Customer satisfaction is all about how happy customers are with the services or products they use. In banking, it refers to how well digital banking services meet the expectations of customers. Essentially, it's about whether customers feel their needs are being met when using things like mobile banking apps, internet banking, or ATMs.

Theoretical Review

This study review is anchored on three theories, namely: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Customer Satisfaction Theory. Each of these theories provides a unique lens through which to explore customer behavior, expectations, and perceptions in the digital banking space.

The Technology Acceptance Model, developed by Fred Davis in 1989, this model explains how people adopt and use new technologies. At its core, TAM revolves around two key ideas: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU).

Perceived Usefulness is how much users believe the technology will improve their tasks or performance. While, Perceived Ease of Use is how effortless they believe using the technology will be.

Applied to digital economy in banking, TAM helps us understand how users in South-south States in Nigeria decide whether or not to embrace digital banking apps, USSD codes, and online platforms. If customers find these digital tools helpful and easy to use, they're more likely to adopt them and stick with them. As usage increases, so does the likelihood of satisfaction. In short, TAM shows us that the simpler and more beneficial the technology feels, the happier the customer becomes.

However, Expectancy-Dis-confirmation theory; proposed by Richard L. Oliver in 1980, explains satisfaction through a very relatable concept: expectation versus reality. The theory states that when people get more than they expected, they're satisfied. When they get less, they're disappointed. Concerning digital economy in banking, if a customer expects a bank's digital platform to be fast, secure, and reliable, and it delivers on all counts, the result is satisfaction. But if otherwise that is slow, glitchy, or unsafe, it will lead to customers dissatisfaction.

Empirical Literature

The empirical reviewed is based on digital platform employed by banks in Nigeria aimed at bank customers satisfaction. For instance; Shariff, Abubakar, and Haruna (2025) investigated the impact of mobile banking on customer satisfaction at selected deposit money banks (DMBs) in Gombe State. The study employed a survey research design. Finding of the study revealed that mobile banking (MBB) has a significant positive influence on customer satisfaction.

Ukwubile and Onwe (2024) studied the relationship between electronic banking services and customer satisfaction in Nigerian deposit money banks. The study employed a survey research design. The findings show that the service reliability of electronic banking has no significant impact on customer satisfaction. Godwin (2024) examined the relationship between financial technology and the business growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Port Harcourt. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. Spearman's Rank Correlation and Partial Correlation. The findings of the study showed that a positive and significant relationship exists between financial technology innovation and business growth. Shariff, Abubakar and Usman (2024) examined the effect of electronic banking service quality on customer satisfaction in deposit money banks. The study methodology is based on the results of the previous studies, the study found that an automated teller machine (ATM) has a positive effect on customer satisfaction, and a point of sale (POS) also has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Yusuf and Ologunwa (2024) examined the effect of digital banking on customers' satisfaction among the deposit money banks in Southwest Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design. The results showed that the deployment of various mobile and internet banking services increases customer satisfaction in the banking sector.

Ajayi, Olutoye, and Abidemi (2023) assessed digital banking as a stimulant of customers' satisfaction in Nigerian deposit money banks. The study adopted a survey research design. The result of the analysis revealed that digital banking is a positive and significant determinant of customer service quality in the Nigerian deposit money bank. Joseph, Ebitu, Maurice, Edim and Asueze (2023) examined electronic banking and customer satisfaction in commercial banks. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The findings revealed that the automated payment system, automated delivery channel, and automated information-sourcing service had significant positive effects on customer satisfaction in commercial banks.

Samuel, Birhan & Bantie (2023) examine the effect of electronic banking (e-Banking) service quality on customer satisfaction in Ethiopia's emerging banking industry. Chi-square correlations and multinomial logistic regression were employed to analyse the quantitative data. The results confirmed a significant effect of the variables responsiveness, reliability, security and privacy, speed, and convenience on customer satisfaction. Similarly, customer satisfaction with the electronic banking service quality has a significant effect on customer loyalty. System availability, ease of use, and service charge, Ismaila and Akintola (2023) examined the effect of electronic banking on customer satisfaction in selected deposit money banks in Ogun State, Nigeria. This study

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adopted a descriptive survey research design. Finding revealed that Electronic banking has a significant effect on customer service security experience, customers' user friendliness experience, accessibility experience, and availability experience in Ogun State. Nwarisi, Igwe & Ozuru (2022) studied the nexus between digital service delivery and the business performance of deposit money banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study adopted an explanatory research design. . The findings of the study showed that digital service delivery insignificantly relates to business performance.. Amadi & Osagie (2020) investigated the relationship between Internet Banking Service Quality and Customer Retention in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design. The result also revealed that customer technology adoption positively influences the relationship between internet banking service quality and customer retention in deposit money banks in Rivers State.

Asuquo & Ezekwe, (2020) studied the impact of electronic banking services on customers' satisfaction in selected Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. A combination of descriptive and inferential statistics was employed as techniques for data analysis. The findings reveal that customers' dissatisfaction emanating from various complaints ranges from arbitrary debiting of customer accounts , non-availability of cash at the ATM, resolution of disputes on the electronic banking products and trapping of customer's card by the ATM etc. Joshua & Akintoye (2020) examined the impact of electronic banking on satisfaction of corporate bank customers in Nigeria. The study adopted survey research designed through the use of structured questionnaire and the regression analysis was the statistical method adopted. The studied found that there is a significant relationship between digital banking and customers' satisfaction. Chimaobi, Akujor and Mbah (2020) examine the impact of electronic banking on customer satisfaction in commercial banks in Imo State. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Techniques was employed for the study data analysis. The result shows that there is a negative relationship between point of sale and customer satisfaction.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design. The study sourced primary data directly from bank customers on digital economy to describe and interpret the impact of digital economy has on bank customers satisfaction in South-south Nigeria. The target population for this study comprises the entire bank customers in the aforementioned states in Nigeria. However, due to a large number of unknown populations of digital economy, the sample size determination was based on infinite population by Godden (2004) as follows;

$$S = \frac{Z^2 P(1 - P)}{C^2}$$

Where :

S = the sample size, P = Percentage of success, C = Confidence interval and Z = Confidence level. With a 95% level of confidence (corresponding value of 1.96), a confidence interval of 0.05(5%), and a Percentage of success is 50%,

The sample size is calculated thus:

$$S = \frac{([1.96])^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{(0.05)^2} = 384.16 \approx \text{Three hundred and eighty-four (384) respondents are the target population. The sample size is estimated at 384.}$$

Thereafter, the study adopted a purposive and random sampling technique to carry out this survey research. In the first stage, following the sample size of 384 determined, the sample size of 384 was then randomly distributed the to six (6) states in South-south of Nigeria namely; Akwa-ibom, Bayesal, Cross-Rivers, Delta, Edo and Rivers. In the second stage, purposive sampling techniques were employed to administer the research instrument to the users of digital channels in banking industries.

Table 1: Combine Explanatory Variables Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.983	5

Source: SPSS Statistics 25 Output from study data

The reliability test in Table 1 shows that all five (5) items, namely, Mobile online banking app (MOA), Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD), Point of Sale (POS), Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) and consumer satisfaction (CS) used in this study meet the test of reliability, the Cronbach Alpha of 0.983 about 98 percent indicate that the instrument used to elicits the data and the content of the instrument are reliable. The data collected in this study is presented using appropriate tables, graphs, percentages, etc, while multiple regression analysis was used to test the research hypothesis using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

Model Specification

In this study, multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the study data. The model specification of this study is as follows;

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$$CS = f(\text{MOB USD POS ATM}) \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

$$CS = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{MOB} + \beta_2\text{USD} + \beta_3\text{POS} + \beta_4\text{ATM} + e \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where;

CS: implies customer satisfaction

MOB: means a Mobile Online Banking Application

USSD: stands for Unstructured Supplementary Service Data

POS is the Point of Sale (POS)

ATM is an Automatic Teller Machine

e is a random variable or other unexplainable factors

In this model, the main parameters of interest are β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 in terms of sign and significance, and the data were measured on a five (5 Likert scale ranging from strongly agreed (SA) to strongly disagreed (SD)).

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Descriptive Analysis

The data generated through the questionnaire were presented descriptively using frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation.

Table 2: Analysis of Questionnaire Administered

Number of Questionnaires Administered	Number of Usable Retrieved Questionnaire	Percentage	Number of Unusable/ Not Retrieved Questionnaire	Percentage
384	372	97	12	3

Source: Author Computation (2024)

Table 2 presents the primary data used in this study. Three hundred eighty-four questionnaires were administered to the respondents; 372 (97%) questionnaires were correctly filled and returned, while 12 (3%) questionnaires were not returned or unusable for several reasons. However, 97% is a good percentage to work with, while the remaining 3% unturned and does not affect the outcome of the findings.

Analysis of Study Research Questions

This section presents an analysis of the descriptive statistics of each explanatory variable and dependent variable as reported in tables 3 to 7

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Mobile Online Banking App (MOB)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I preferred the Mobile online banking app (MOB) to other digital banking apps	372	1	5	4.20	.890
I often use the Mobile online banking app (MOB)	372	1	5	4.23	.950
Mobile online banking app (MOB Gives Customers Satisfaction	372	1	5	4.24	.893
Mobile Online Banking App (Mob) is Convenient, Fast, and Effective to use	372	2	5	4.10	.898
Valid N (listwise)	372			4.19	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The result shows ground mean scores of 4.19. This is far above three, representing the mean of the range of scores (5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 for strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree, respectively).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I preferred Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) to other digital banking services	372	1	5	4.23	.886

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I often use unstructured supplementary service data (USSD)	372	1	5	4.32	.874
Unstructured Supplementary Service data (USSD) is Convenient, Fast, and Effective to use	372	1	5	4.24	.942
Unstructured Supplementary Service data (USSD) Gives Customers Satisfaction	372	1	5	4.24	.942
Valid N (listwise)	372			4.26	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The result shows ground mean scores of 4.26. This is far above three, which represents the criterion mean of five-point Likert scale.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Point of Sale (POS)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I often use Point of Sale (POS)	372	2	5	4.10	.903
I preferred Point of Sale (POS) to other digital banking	372	1	5	4.24	.897
Point of Sale (POS) is Convenient, Fast, and Effective to use	372	1	5	4.22	.964
Point of Sale (POS) Gives Customer Satisfaction	372	1	5	4.27	.951
Valid N (listwise)	372			4.2	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The result shows ground mean scores of 4.2. This is far above three, which represents the criterion mean of five-point Likert scale.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I often use an Automated Teller Machine (ATM)	372	1	5	4.14	.917
I preferred the Automated Teller Machine (ATM) to other digital banking services	372	1	5	3.89	1.164
Automated Teller Machine (ATM) is Convenient, Fast, and Effective to use	372	1	5	4.10	1.091
Automated Teller Machine (ATM) Gives Customers Satisfaction	372	1	5	4.10	1.091
Valid N (listwise)	372			4.04	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The result shows ground mean scores of 4.04 above criterion mean of 3

Table 7 Descriptive Statistics Consumer Satisfaction (CS)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer Satisfaction Includes Timely Service Delivery	372	1	5	4.20	.851
Customer Satisfaction Includes Convenient Service Delivery	372	1	5	4.05	1.103
Customer Satisfaction Includes Effective Service Delivery	372	1	5	4.06	1.095
Customer Satisfaction Includes Availability of Service	372	1	5	4.01	.996
Valid N (listwise)	372			4.08	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The result shows ground mean scores of 4.08. This is far above three, (3) which represents the criterion mean of five-point Likert scale.

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Test of Hypotheses

The four (4) hypotheses formulated in section One were tested using the multiple regression statistics at a 5% significance level with the aid of the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) version 25. Decision criterion: Reject the stated null hypothesis if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 and accept the alternative hypothesis if it is the other way round. The multiple regression results are presented in Tables 8 to 11 as follows;

Table 8: Multiple Regression Analysis Variable Entered

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	MOB, USSD, POS, ATM ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: CS

b. All requested variables entered.

Source: SPSS Statistics 25

Table 8 presents the variables understudy. The explanatory variables in this model are Mobile online banking app (MOB), Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD). Point of Sale (POS) and Automatic Teller Machine (ATM), which served as independent variables while, customer satisfaction (CS) serve as dependent variable. The entire variables specified in the model were captured.

Table 9: Multiple Regression Analysis Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.990 ^a	.980	.979	.14180

a. Predictors: (Constant), MOB, USSD, POS, ATM

Source: SPSS Statistics 25

Table 9 presents a summary of the multiple regression model, which provides the result of R, R², adjusted R², and the standard error of the estimate. This model summary is used to determine how well a regression model fits the data: The value of R is the multiple correlation coefficient, which is used to measure the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable; A value of .990 is about 99percent, in this study, indicates a good level of prediction. The R² value, also called the coefficient of determination, is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables (technically, it is the proportion of variation accounted for by the regression model above and beyond the mean model). The R² value is .980 representing 98%, indicating variability in the dependent variable due to change in the independent variables. In other words, the study's independent variables explain approximately 98% variability of the dependent variable.

Generally, the model summary of this test indicates a high and positive correlation between the identified digital banking channels and customers satisfaction (R = 0.990). Also, the R² = 0.980 indicates that 98% of variation in the dependent variable (customers satisfaction) was explained by the independent variable (digital banking channels), while the remaining 2% can be explained outside the model.

Table 10: Multiple Regression Analysis ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	355.230	4	88.807	4416.556	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.380	367	.020		
	Total	362.609	371			

a. Dependent Variable: CS

b. Predictors: (Constant), MOB, USSD, POS, ATM

Source: SPSS Statistics 25

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Table 10 presents multiple regression analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests used to determine the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable. The ANOVA result, which shows that $F = 4416.556$; $P = 0.000 < 0.05$, indicates that on the aggregate, the digital banking channels (MOB, USSD, POS, ATM) are statistically significant predictors of consumer satisfactions of money deposit banks customers in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 11: Multiple Regression Analysis of the Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.239	.042		-5.651	.000
	MOB	.864	.073	.769	11.798	.000
	USSD	.118	.050	.105	2.365	.019
	POS	-.498	.089	-.462	-5.608	.000
	ATM	.559	.039	.587	14.334	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CS

Source: **SPSS Statistics 25**

Mathematically; the model estimation is: $CS = b_0 + b_1MOB_1 + b_2USSD_2 + b_3POS + b_4ATM_4$

$CS = -.239 + .864b_1 + .1188b_2 + -.498b_3 + .559b_4$

$t = [-5.651] [11.798] [2.365] [-5.608] [14.334]$

$Sig = (.000) (.000) (.019) (.000) (.000)$

The Coefficients indicate how much the dependent variable varies with each independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant. Given the calculated t-values and significant values, the result revealed that at 5% significance, the explanatory variables are statistically significant. The Coefficient of fixed variable, that is, constant (C), also known as the intercept, is the value of customers satisfaction (CS) when other independent variables have a value of zero is -.239 is statically significant with a probability value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05 level of significance i.e, at 5%. This result suggests that about 23.9% of changes or declines in CS is associated with other factors not explained by any of the explanatory variables stated in the model.

The result shows that Mobile online banking app with a coefficient value of ($\beta = .864$; $t=11.798$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in a Mobile online banking app affects 86.4% positive change in a customer satisfaction This implies that Mobile online banking is a statistically significant predictor of customer satisfaction. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, which states, "Digital economy" via Mobile online banking app does not have any significant impact on bank customer satisfaction. Hence, Digital economy via mobile online banking app significantly affects customer satisfaction positively.

The result shows that Unstructured Supplementary Service Data with a coefficient value of ($\beta = .118$; $t=2.365$; $p = 0.019 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in Unstructured Supplementary Service Data affects about 12% positive change in a customer satisfaction This implies that Unstructured Supplementary Service Data is a statistically significant predictor of customer satisfaction Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, which states that Unstructured Supplementary Service Data does not significantly impact bank customer satisfaction Nigeria". The result shows that a Point of Sale (POS) with a coefficient value of ($\beta = -0.498$; $t = -5.608$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in Point of Sale (POS) affects 49.8% about 50% decline in a customer satisfaction. This implies that Point of Sale (POS) is a statistically significant predictor of customer satisfaction. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, which states otherwise,

The result shows that Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) with a coefficient value of ($\beta = 0.559$; $t = 14.334$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicates that a one percent increase in Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) effects 55.9%, approximately 56% positive change in a customer satisfaction. This implies that Automatic Teller Machine (ATM).. is a statistically significant predictor of customer satisfaction. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, which states, "Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) does not have any significant impact on customer satisfaction Nigeria.

The foregoing findings suggest that digital economy have positive and statistically significant impact on bank customers satisfaction.

5. CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the impact of digital economy on bank customers satisfaction in South-south States of Nigeria. The specific objectives include examining the impact of the digital economy via mobile online banking app, Unstructured Supplementary

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Service Data (USSD), Point of Sale (POS) and Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) on bank customer satisfaction. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that digital economy has positive and significant impacts on bank customers satisfaction. As manifested from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested;

That digital economy via digital banking channels should be embracing and encourage by all Nigerian and, that governments at all levels should formulate and implement the policies that will improve the use of digital economy. Also, stakeholders in financial sector should improving digital economy infrastructures that will aid the performance of the digital banking channels as well as contributes to customer satisfaction.

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